

Welfare Schemes for Tribes in West Bengal (2011-2020)

Hriday Dalal

*Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Political Science, The University of Burdwan,
Assistant professor in Political science Aghorekamini Prakashchandra Mahavidyalaya*

ABSTRACT

India is a homeland of above seven hundred tribes, they share 6 percent total population. West Bengal is one of the states among 29 states in India. As per the official website provided by the government of West Bengal there are forty tribal communities are living in the states and their populations are above fifty lakhs. New government came in power in 2011, started various welfare and socio-economic development scheme for tribes living in West Bengal. Most of the tribes started their development with the help of governmental initiatives. The primary objective of my paper is to find out welfare scheme taken by new regimes of government and conclude tribal development.

KEYWORDS: *Tribe, Welfare scheme, governmental initiatives, tribal status.*

Objective of Paper:

1. To analyse the meaning of Tribe.
2. To identify major tribe living in the state of West Bengal.
3. To discuss welfare scheme for tribe taken by government of West Bengal.
4. To identify major cause of backwardness in tribe living in West Bengal.

Tribes an overall concept:

Merriam webster dictionary discussed about tribes, tribes mean a social group composed chiefly of numerous families, clans, or generations having a shared ancestry and language. They also discussed tribe is a political division of the Roman people originally representing one of the three original tribes of ancient Rome and a category of taxonomic classification ranking below a subfamily.

(<https://www.merriam-webster.com/>)

Cambridge dictionary explains tribe as a group of people, often of related families, who live together, sharing the same language, culture, and history, especially those who do not live in towns or cities. (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org>)

Tribe, in anthropology, a notional form of human social organization based on a set of smaller groups (known as bands), having temporary or permanent political integration, and defined by traditions of common descent, language, culture, and ideology.

The term originated in ancient Rome, where the word *tribus* denoted a division within the state. It later came into use as a way to describe the cultures encountered through European exploration. By the mid-19th century, many anthropologists and other scholars were using the term, as well as band, chiefdom, and state, to denote particular stages in unilineal cultural evolution.

Although unilineal cultural evolution is no longer a credible theory, these terms continue to be used as a sort of technical shorthand in college courses, documentaries, and popular reference works. In

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such contexts, members of a tribe are typically said to share a self-name and a contiguous territory; to work together in such joint endeavours as trade, agriculture, house construction, warfare, and ceremonial activities; and to be composed of a number of smaller local communities such as bands or villages. In addition, they may be aggregated into higher-order clusters, such as nations.

As an anthropological term, the word tribe fell out of favour in the latter part of the 20th century. Some anthropologists rejected the term itself, on the grounds that it could not be precisely defined. Others objected to the negative connotations that the word acquired in the colonial context. Scholars of Africa, in particular, felt that it was pejorative as well as inaccurate. Thus, many anthropologists replaced it with the designation ethnic group, usually defined as a group of people with a common ancestry and language, a shared cultural and historical tradition, and an identifiable territory. Ethnic group is a particularly appropriate term within the discussion of modernizing countries, where one's identity and claims to landownership may depend less on extended kinship ties than on one's natal village or region of origin. (<https://www.britannica.com>)

The Imperial Gazetteer of India, 1911, defines a tribe as a "collection of families bearing a common name, speaking a common dialect, occupying or professing to occupy a common territory and is not usually endogamous though originally it might have been so". For Romans, the tribe was a political division. The Dictionary of Anthropology mentions tribe as a social group, usually with a definite area, dialect, cultural homogeneity and unifying social organization. The tribes in India differ from one another depending upon the region, language, customs, culture, religion, racial traits and so on. Often a tribe possesses a distinct dialect and distinct cultural traits. In the West, as also in India, the word tribe initially had a totally different connotation than what is prevalent now (Verma, 1990, pp, 62-68).

H. H. Risley in his book 'Tribes and Caste of Bengal Vol-II' discussed, In India, tribal people are known by many names, such as 'adivasi' (original settlers), 'scheduled tribes' (anusuchit janajati), 'tribes', 'janajati' (folk communities), 'girijan' (hill dwellers), 'vanvasi' (forest dwellers), 'vanyajati' (forest caste), adimjati (primitive caste) 'hill tribe' (mountain dwellers) and indigenous people. The tribal people of India are called 'Scheduled Tribes' in the Indian constitution. The indigenous people of India prefer calling themselves Adivasi (original inhabitants). The word Adi means "first", "original" or "from the earliest time", and the word Vasi means "dweller", "inhabitant", and "resident of". This self-identification as Adivasi corresponds to the modern concept of indigenous peoples. (Risley, 1871, pp, 28-32)

Major tribes in West Bengal

Presently there are forty tribal communities with 52 lakh 96 thousand 943 population living in the state of West Bengal and they shared 5.5 percentage of total population. The major tribes are Santal, Munda, Bhumij, Kora, Oraon, Ho. The below chart shows that five major tribes living in the state of West Bengal sharing total 84.4 percent of total ST population in 2001 and 76.6 percent of ST population in 2011.

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Source: The Census of India, 2011

The above pie chart shows as the Census 2011, tribes among Santal, Bhumij, Tamang, Oraon, Munda, Kora, Lodha shares their population in above 3 percent and others 33 tribes shares below 3 percent of tribal population in West Bengal.

Welfare scheme for tribes

- **Income Generated Scheme:** The government of West Bengal made arrangements for income generated schemes for tribes living in the state of West Bengal.
- ✓ Under the scheme the government has taken initiatives to empower tribal people in, animal husbandry, small scale business, horticulture, and fisheries. agriculture, state government provided irrigation facilities.
- ✓ for animal husbandry, the government of West Bengal helped tribes by providing baby animals.
- ✓ the government of West Bengal provided loan for small scale business to tribes
- ✓ the government provided financial aid for horticulture, fisheries to tribals. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)
- **Infrastructure Development:** For tribal development of infrastructures in tribal areas, government of West Bengal made poultry farms, goat shades, piggery shades, various link roads, bridges, culverts, deep tube wells for agriculture. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)
- **Job Oriented Training Programme:** The government of West Bengal arranged job-oriented training programmes like PSC, CHSL, CGL, combined courses, and offer various computer training courses and spoken English classes to enhance their skills. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)
- **PVTGs:** Three Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups are living in the state of West Bengal. The Three tribes are (i) Toto (ii) Birhor , and (iii) Lodha. In the financial year 2018-19 the Government of India provided 574 lakh rupees for development of three PVTGs. Government of West Bengal provided them various facilities, like school bags, pens, mosquito nets, community

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hall, community water filter, making school building with Guard wall, residential School attached hostels, small scale irrigation facilities etc. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

- **Kendu Leaves Collector Social Security Scheme, 2015:** The government of West Bengal provides social security scheme for tribes who collect Kendu leaves. This scheme introduced in 2015 in three districts in West Bengal are Bankura, Purulia and Paschim Medinipur. The scheme covers tribal people who collect Kendu leaves from forest up to the age of years in the threat of snake bite, elephants attack and storm. Till 2023, 35000 are received such type of facilities.

(<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

- **Joi Johar scheme:** Joi Johar scheme benefited 40 tribal communities living in the state. The state government provided monthly incentive of Rs.1000 to individuals to the age above 60 years. More than 3 lakh beneficiaries are getting benefits from the project. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

- **Sikhasree:** The government of West Bengal provided annual Rs.800 scholarship to the tribal students of class V to VIII of people within the tribes. Approximate 18 lakh beneficiaries availing this scheme. Four types of scholarship provided by the government of West Bengal under Sikhasree, these are (i) monthly Rs.1200 scholarship to the students pursuing Medicine, Engineering, M. Phil, Ph.D., LL.M.; (ii) Monthly 1000/- rupees scholarship for B. Pharm, LLB, post-graduation, Hotel Management, Nursing students. (iii) Monthly 1000/- rupees scholarship for hostellers of under graduate courses. (iv) Monthly 1000/- rupees scholarship for hosteller students of class XI, XII, ITI, polytechnics.

(<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

Adivasi Shikha Rinn Yojana 2012-2013: The government of West Bengal provided educational loan for tribal students who are pursuing in professional course. After getting job, beneficiaries would repay their loan with 6% annual interest. For this scheme government of West Bengal has already disbursed 130.369 lakh rupees for development of tribal students.

(<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

- **Hostel Facilities:** The government of West Bengal made arrangements for tribal students to enrich their education by providing them three kind of hostel facilities.

(i) Centre: This kind of hostel facilities can be availed by any tribal students who have passed secondary examination. There are 30 hostels all over the state of West Bengal.

(ii) Hostel Grants: For making School attached hostels and providing hostel facilities, the government of West Bengal has provided financial aid. there are 49500 beneficiaries availing facility under this scheme. Tribal students under BPL categories getting benefit from 1301 new hostels by which are 40000 students benefited.

(iii) Ashram Schools: The government of West Bengal has made 247 School attached with hostel facilities for tribal students. Present hostel occupancy stands at 12384, and they getting monthly Rs.1000 as scholarship. presently 235 Ashram School are operational across state.

(<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

- **Merit-cum-Means Scholarship:** Monthly Rs. 400 has been provided to the students of BPL tribal communities who are residing in hostels for class X-XII. For the BPL tribal student studying in class V-Vi getting monthly 100 rupees and in class VII-X getting monthly Rs.125 scholarship also under merit Cum means scholarship. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)

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- **Eklavya Model Residential School:** There are total 7 EMRS in the state of West Bengal. The schools are located in the district of Bankura, Purulia, Paschim Medinipur, Jhargram, Jalpaiguri, Birbhum, Dakshin Dinajpur. The medium of education of these schools is English. Each school have 420 seat therefore total 2826 students are getting benefit from these schools. The government of West Bengal is providing all kind of facilities like hostel fees, examination fees, admission fees, School dresses, book and other educational tools. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)
- **Pandit Raghunath Murmu Residential School:** There are total 9 schools for schedule tribes students operating under the name of Pandit Raghunath Murmu Residential School throughout the state. The teaching medium of these schools is Bengali. These schools have hostel facilities. The students get monthly Rs.1000 as scholarship. (<https://adibasikalyan.gov.in/about-the-ministry>)
- **Belpahari Residential Government Girls High School:** A fully tribal residential Girls High School was inaugurated in the district of Paschim Medinipur at Belpahari block. There are 317 tribal girls benefiting from this school.

Conclusion and findings

The aim of my paper is to analyse various welfare scheme taken by govt of West Bengal and identify major reason of backwardness among tribes. Researcher finds various hindrance of tribal development among tribes, first, among forty tribes 36 tribes have below 50 percent rate of literacy, especially those are living in main land, so; literacy is one of the primary causes of their backwardness. Second, identity politics in West Bengal has not been properly organised by political parties and tribal leader. Third, most of the tribal communities are unknown of welfare scheme taken by government of West Bengal, it indicates communication gap. Fourth, Right to Education Act-2009 was not properly implemented in tribal areas, it is a major cause. Fifth, Xaxa committies identifies language barrier is a cause of tribal backwardness. Sixth, there are three PVTGs are living in the states, their literacy is below 30 percent, central as well as states government has taken welfare scheme for their upliftment but their development has not noticeable. Researcher suggests three initiatives, first, states government should take advertise programme, that means publicly and privately advertise governmental scheme and could appoint a film star as a brand ambassador. Second, local NGOs should take part to development of tribe. Third, it is responsible of Mainstream people to support tribal people and treat them as not a human being but as a citizen. :Top Five Tribal G

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